

D9.1

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Table of contents

1	Executive summary.....	5
2	Detailed report on the deliverable	6
2.1	Background/Introduction.....	6
	Project introduction	6
	Purpose of the deliverable.....	6
2.2	Target audiences & messages	6
	Overall message	6
	Audience-specific messages	6
	Scientific community.....	7
	Private institutions.....	7
	Partner sites.....	7
	Member country representatives.....	8
	Candidate country representatives.....	8
	Funding bodies	8
	General public	8
2.3	Communication & dissemination means.....	9
	Branding material.....	9
	Communication & dissemination channels	9
	Website.....	9
	Social media.....	9
	Newsletter	10
	Publications	10
	Success stories.....	10
	Mass media.....	11
	Communication & dissemination venues.....	11
	Conferences.....	11
	Training events	11

Internal stakeholder meetings	11
External stakeholder meetings	11
Local events for citizens	11
Alignment with IMPULSE workplan	13
WP1 Long-term sustainability & access procedures.....	13
WP2 Creating a repository of community compounds	13
WP3–6 New scientific services and data management protocols	13
WP7 Training and capacity building	13
WP8 Engagement with public–private initiatives	13
WP9 Outreach & Dissemination.....	13
Working group.....	14
2.4 Key performance indicators.....	14
3 Conclusions/Next steps	14

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial intelligence
AoM	Assembly of Members
EACL	European Academic Compound Library
ECBD	European Chemical Biology Database
ERA	European Research Area
ERC	European Research Council
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ILO	Industry Liaison Office
IMPULSE	Improving User Experience, Long-Term Sustainability, and Services of EU-OPENSREEN
IP	Intellectual property
KPI	Key performance indicator
ML	Machine learning
PSF	Partner Site Forum
SME	Small- or medium-sized enterprise
RI	Research infrastructure

WP

Work package

1 Executive summary

The EU-OPENSSCREEN, the leading European Research Infrastructure (RI) for chemical biology and early drug discovery, supports researchers by offering high caliber services in high-throughput screening and medicinal chemistry. Under the IMPULSE project, a consortium of 24 EU-OPENSSCREEN partners is collaborating to expand the service offerings of EU-OPENSSCREEN and enhance the RI's long-term sustainability and benefit to the scientific community.

To successfully promote the ongoing work of the EU-OPENSSCREEN and IMPULSE consortia and to showcase their value to scientists in Europe and beyond, partners across both consortia are encouraged to engage in regular communication with several audiences. To facilitate this process and unify the messages projected by the consortia, this Communication Plan was developed in line with the 'RI-VIS Communication Standards Toolkit' from the EU-funded Horizon 2020 project RI-VIS (Grant Agreement No. 824063) to identify the target audiences, the key messages for each, and the communication and dissemination means used.

2 Detailed report on the deliverable

2.1 Background/Introduction

Project introduction

The EU-OPENSSCREEN European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) is a distributed network of European research institutions supporting chemical biology and early drug discovery research. The IMPULSE consortium combines the cutting-edge expertise and resources of 24 partner institutions to advance the capacities and sustainability of the EU-OPENSSCREEN ERIC by diversifying funding sources, expanding ERIC membership, broadening the user community, enhancing service offerings, improving service quality, optimising the use of existing resources and leveraging partnerships with other research infrastructures (RIs) and stakeholders.

Purpose of the deliverable

Given the IMPULSE project's mission to enhance the capacities of EU-OPENSSCREEN, the communication and dissemination goals for IMPULSE are tightly intertwined with those of EU-OPENSSCREEN. The purpose of this deliverable is therefore to outline a clear and effective strategy for the communication and dissemination of ongoing activities, outcomes and developments within both EU-OPENSSCREEN and the IMPULSE project consortia (henceforth referred to as '*the Consortia*'). Through an analysis of all stakeholder groups relevant to the Consortia, targeted communication and dissemination messages can be aligned to each to raise awareness of both and promote their offerings to all relevant audiences.

To achieve this goal, the present Communication Plan addresses three broad themes:

- **Target audiences** and the messages tailored to each
- **Measures and tools** for project communication and dissemination
- **Key performance indicators** to measure the success of the communication and dissemination actions

An additional section of this Communication Plan is dedicated to the communication and dissemination activities planned specifically in the IMPULSE workplan (see page 13, 'Alignment with IMPULSE workplan').

2.2 Target audiences & messages

Overall message

All communication and dissemination activities for the Consortia will emphasise the common mission of EU-OPENSSCREEN:

To provide a trusted research infrastructure to chemical biology researchers seeking technology, compound, data and training services.

Beyond this message, IMPULSE outreach will emphasise the relationship between the Consortia:

IMPULSE is an EU-funded initiative which supports the growth and sustainability of EU-OPENSSCREEN by expanding its scientific service offerings, addressing gaps in training and extending its international reach.

Audience-specific messages

Due to the manifold goals of EU-OPENSSCREEN and the IMPULSE project, the Consortia actively engage with several audiences. This Communication Plan outlines each relevant audience and the messages curated for each.

Scientific community

The scientific community includes life science researchers in both academia and industry. EU-OPENSSCREEN offers significant value to the scientific community through its established services in high-throughput screening and medicinal chemistry, as well as its robust training programme. The Consortia will continue to boost this message to scientists in Europe and beyond to promote the credibility of EU-OPENSSCREEN and attract new collaborators. Special emphasis will be placed on communicating about the progress and ultimate incorporation of the new services developed within IMPULSE into the EU-OPENSSCREEN portfolio of services.

Outreach to specific prospective collaborator communities will also be conducted with tailored messages:

- **Biologists:** EU-OPENSSCREEN offers access to state-of-the-art screening platforms and expertise to help biologists overcome bottlenecks in their drug discovery projects. Biologists benefit from access to EU-OPENSSCREEN's unique compound collections, which can be screened to identify high-quality tool compounds for early target validation. Under IMPULSE, new advanced services are being developed and integrated to the screening and hit optimisation offers.
- **Chemists:** EU-OPENSSCREEN hosts a novel compound-sharing initiative, which allows under-exploited compounds to be exposed to a wide range of biological targets. Chemists are invited to submit compounds to EU-OPENSSCREEN's European Academic Compound Library (EACL), where they will be stored, assessed for biological activities and integrated into screening campaigns across the network. Compounds identified as 'hits' may trigger new collaborations between the compound-owning chemist and the biologist involved in the screening campaign. All intellectual property (IP) remains with the compound submitter.
- **Data scientists:** Data scientists have open access to our large-scale, high-quality database, the European Chemical Biology Database (ECBD, <https://ecbd.eu/>), where data from bioprofiling and in-network screening campaigns are deposited. IMPULSE is further enhancing EU-OPENSSCREEN's data management and interoperability practices.

Private institutions

The Consortia will communicate with an audience of professionals at private institutions, including pharmaceutical/biotechnology companies, start-ups, and small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs); reagent providers, equipment manufacturers; software developers; foundations; and/or charities. Professionals targeted in these institutions are industry researchers and managers who may or may not have a scientific background.

The messages communicated to private institutions will mirror those for the general scientific community, with an additional emphasis on the following points:

- EU-OPENSSCREEN enables **co-development of technology** with added value for the private institution. These co-development projects achieve both cost and time reductions in the drug discovery process.
- Collaboration with EU-OPENSSCREEN helps private institutions further **extend or validate** their product's capabilities.
- EU-OPENSSCREEN collaborations operate on a **pre-competitive model** based on **open innovation**.

Partner sites

Both EU-OPENSSCREEN and IMPULSE are driven by the efforts of and collaborations among EU-OPENSSCREEN partner sites. When communicating with partner sites, EU-OPENSSCREEN will therefore emphasise the value of active participation in the consortia, including the following benefits:

- Leverage public investment into basic research
- Save time and costs through EU-OPENSSCREEN's defined pipeline for project sourcing and execution
- Collaborative opportunities leading to joint projects, shared expertise

- Centralised management of access to partner facilities

Member country representatives

As an ERIC, EU-OPENSSCREEN receives annual funding from member countries to sustain its activities and improve its offers to the scientific community. Each EU-OPENSSCREEN member country elects country-specific representatives with whom we maintain regular contact to explain the status of the ERIC. The following messages are communicated to member country representatives:

- Sharing bundled expertise **saves time and expense** and **leverages public investment** made into basic research.
- EU-OPENSSCREEN is utilising member fees to **strategically and proactively address the needs** of the European chemical biology sphere.
- IMPULSE is establishing new capabilities at screening/chemistry sites, ensuring data reproducibility, refining operational standards, integrating ML/AI methods, reinforcing ongoing training and outreach.

Candidate country representatives

EU-OPENSSCREEN holds regular discussions with representatives of countries interested in joining the ERIC ("candidate countries"). As these representatives symbolise prospective funders of the ERIC, targeted communications towards this audience focus on the benefits of participating in and supporting EU-OPENSSCREEN:

- EU-OPENSSCREEN addresses **grand societal challenges** such as health and wellbeing of ageing societies, food security, disease prevention and the development of personalised treatments of diseases.
- EU-OPENSSCREEN builds upon and integrates Europe's preexisting assets and facilities in chemical biology and **improves the competitiveness** of the European Research Area (ERA).
- Sharing bundled expertise **saves time and expense** and **leverages public investment** made into basic research.
- EU-OPENSSCREEN drives innovative collaboration by providing **high quality services** to scientists and **supplying a link** between basic and applied research.
- Participation in EU-OPENSSCREEN allows member countries the opportunity to **showcase national research** and achievements on an international stage.

Funding bodies

Current and prospective funders of EU-OPENSSCREEN ERIC include individuals and organisations on the national, international and European level. It is critical to stay in contact with such organisations to secure funding for the sustained provision of services to the scientific community. Key messages to current and prospective funding bodies include the following:

- Activities conducted within the Consortia have **high value for the everyday lives** of European citizens across several sectors, including healthcare, agriculture and food security.
- EU-OPENSSCREEN promotes the efficient development of **novel or improved therapies** for patients.
- EU-OPENSSCREEN actions are addressing several **United Nations Sustainable Development Goals**, including ensuring healthy lives and promoting well-being for all at all ages; building resilient infrastructure and fostering innovation; and achieving gender equality.
- EU-OPENSSCREEN has **high impact** within Europe through high-calibre research projects and European Research Council (ERC) grants.

General public

EU-OPENSSCREEN communication efforts include reaching out to general audiences with an interest in science and innovation. These audiences may or may not have a background in science.

When communicating to general audiences, EU-OPENSSCREEN will highlight the importance and relevance of chemical biology and drug discovery for the everyday lives of citizens. Specific topics to highlight include the following statements:

- Chemical biology research helps scientists find **valuable new substances** for numerous potential applications, ranging from healthcare to agricultural to cosmetic.
- Early drug discovery research helps us find **safer and more effective treatments** for various diseases, which has a positive impact on healthcare systems down the line.

EU-OPENSREEN will also dedicate some outreach efforts towards explaining the concept of a research infrastructure and how our research infrastructure supports the activities described above.

2.3 Communication & dissemination means

Branding material

To ensure a unified visual identity for all print and online communications for the Consortia, a suite of branded materials have been prepared for communications pertaining to each.

Branded outreach materials for IMPULSE, including visual identity and style, logos, document templates and prepared posters and slide decks, are available to project partners on the “IMPULSE” SharePoint.¹ The EU-OPENSREEN materials and guidelines are available to consortium partner sites on the “EU-OPENSREEN Partner Sites” SharePoint.²

Communication & dissemination channels

The Consortia use several tailored communication channels and activities to reach their target audiences.

Website

The EU-OPENSREEN website³ is the main hub for all communications related to EU-OPENSREEN. The EU-OPENSREEN website also hosts a subpage dedicated to IMPULSE⁴, containing detailed information about the project. Due to the significant overlap between activities in the Consortia, IMPULSE news and updates will be posted in the main EU-OPENSREEN news feed but will always specifically acknowledge IMPULSE.

Social media

The Consortia also share social media accounts (LinkedIn⁵ and X⁶) to quickly and regularly communicate information and updates. These channels are aimed towards an audience with a scientific background and basic knowledge in chemical biology and early drug discovery at minimum. These platforms are used to reach and engage with the scientific community both within and beyond the Consortia.

Table 1 details the hashtags used for both accounts for common post themes. More specific hashtags may be used depending on the post topic (e.g., project-specific hashtags, research topics).

Table 1 Social media hashtags by theme

Post theme	Hashtag(s) used
EU-OPENSREEN general	#EUOPENSREEN #ChemicalBiology #DrugDiscovery

¹ [Communication_outreach](#)

² [Style guide, Templates and Logos](#)

³ <https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/>

⁴ <https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/projects/impulse.html>

⁵ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eu-openscreen/>

⁶ <https://twitter.com/EuOpenscreen>

Partner site news	#EUOSPartnerSite #Collaboration
Scientific result	#Research #Innovation #Screening #MedicinalChemistry #MedChem #Collaboration
European research infrastructure news	#EU_RIs
EU project news	#HorizonEU
IMPULSE	#EUOSImpulse #HorizonEU

EU-OPENSSCREEN also operates a YouTube channel⁷ containing informational videos about the ERIC and recordings of webinars hosted within the ERIC’s training programme. These videos are also available directly on the EU-OPENSSCREEN website to maximise their visibility and accessibility.

Newsletter

Newsletters are an effective way to summarise recent achievements and upcoming events within the ERIC and to communicate them to a wide audience. EU-OPENSSCREEN has an established newsletter of over 40 editions which reaches over 1,500 subscribers.

EU-OPENSSCREEN prepares and distributes a newsletter approximately every three months. A dedicated section of the newsletter is used to provide IMPULSE-specific updates.

Publications

Publications in scientific journals are a critical way to make scientific results and advances available to the wider research community, as their readerships inherently extend beyond the EU-OPENSSCREEN and IMPULSE communities. Furthermore, publishing results in reputable peer-reviewed journals underscores the credibility of the Consortia.

EU-OPENSSCREEN supports several scientific projects per year, many of which are the basis for scientific publications. Projects which received funding from EU-OPENSSCREEN and/or IMPULSE must acknowledge this.

The following acknowledgement statement is used for IMPULSE:

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101132028, project IMPULSE.

The following acknowledgement statement is used for EU-OPENSSCREEN screening projects:

The USER/partner site acknowledges EU-OPENSSCREEN ERIC for providing its COMPOUND COLLECTION for the presented scientific work.

Success stories

EU-OPENSSCREEN writes success stories featuring individual user projects to promote the scientific outcomes of these projects and highlight the services provided at EU-OPENSSCREEN partner sites. Success stories are written in collaboration with users and researchers at the partner sites. Success stories are posted on the EU-OPENSSCREEN website and promoted on the EU-OPENSSCREEN social media channels.

⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/@eu-openscreeneric6048>

Mass media

Significant news from the Consortia is communicated through press releases. News pieces meriting press releases include project launches and significant personnel changes. Press releases are distributed via social media, the EU-OPENSSCREEN website and local outlets (e.g., Campus Berlin-Buch news feed). Partner site representatives serve as main contacts for media dissemination and inquiries.

Communication & dissemination venues

To enable direct person-to-person communication about EU-OPENSSCREEN and IMPULSE with various target audiences, members of both consortia will organise and/or attend several events. The types of events are enumerated below.

Conferences

External conferences are an important way to spread awareness of and promote outcomes from the Consortia. Regular attendance of consortium partners at such events ensures that information reaches diverse audiences. Examples of key events include the following:

- European Chemical Biology Symposium (ECBS)
- International Chemical Biology Society (ICBS) annual meetings
- Federation of European Biochemical Societies (FEBS) Congress
- Society for Laboratory Automation and Screening (SLAS) Conference
- European Federation for Medicinal Chemistry (EFMC) symposia
- European Laboratory Research & Innovation Group (ELRIG) conferences/forums
- European Molecular Biology Organisation (EMBO) conferences/forums

Training events

Both EU-OPENSSCREEN and IMPULSE use regular training events to maintain direct contact with the scientific community. Such events include workshops, training schools and webinars. Training events funded or hosted by EU-OPENSSCREEN and/or IMPULSE include consortium members in the programme, thereby giving visibility to the consortium and its scientific services. Training events aim to prepare the scientific user community to engage with our services in future collaboration projects.

Internal stakeholder meetings

EU-OPENSSCREEN maintains regular contact with internal stakeholders who support and/or fund the ERIC's activities.

One such internal stakeholder group is the EU-OPENSSCREEN Partner Site Forum (PSF), comprising the representatives of each EU-OPENSSCREEN partner site. The PSF convenes twice per year to advise and support the EU-OPENSSCREEN Director General on matters related to the EU-OPENSSCREEN workplan. PSF meetings are a valuable opportunity to communicate information to all partner sites at once.

The EU-OPENSSCREEN central office also liaises with the Assembly of Members (AoM), the highest governing body in the EU-OPENSSCREEN ERIC. The AoM consists of up to two representatives per member/observer country in the ERIC. The AoM convenes twice per year to receive updates on the status of the ERIC as well as analyses of past activities and upcoming workplan projections.

External stakeholder meetings

The Consortia engage in discussions with external funders and collaborators, such as candidate country representatives, European-level organisations and private institutions, to explain the value of funding and/or collaborating with EU-OPENSSCREEN. These meetings take the form of one-on-one discussions, roundtables and joint communications with other research infrastructures and consortia.

Local events for citizens

The Consortia will seek out local science communication events geared toward the general public where they can discuss EU-OPENSSCREEN and communicate the key messages outlined for general audiences.

All target audiences, key messages, and means of outreach are summarised below in Table 2.

Table 2 Summary of target audiences, messages and means of outreach

Audience	Key message(s)	Channel(s)
Scientific community	EU-OPENSSCREEN offers significant value to the scientific community through its established services in high-throughput screening and medicinal chemistry, its database as well as its robust training programme.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conferences • Scientific publications • Training events • Website • Social media • Newsletter
Private institutions	EU-OPENSSCREEN enables pre-competitive co-development of technology to both achieve cost/time reductions and help private institutions further extend or validate their product's capabilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External stakeholder meetings / one-on-one and roundtable settings • Conferences / exhibitions / industry networking events • Scientific publications • Website • Social media • Industry Liaison Office (see below)
Partner sites	Participation in the Consortia offers several benefits, including leveraging public investment into basic research, saving time/costs in drug discovery, and access to collaborative opportunities/shared expertise.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Newsletter • Partner Site Forum
Funding bodies	Activities conducted within the Consortia have high value for the everyday lives of European citizens across several sectors.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External stakeholder meetings / personal communication with funders • Success stories
Member country representatives	EU-OPENSSCREEN is utilising member fees to strategically/proactively address the needs of the European chemical biology sphere.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assembly of Members meeting
Candidate country representatives	<p>EU-OPENSSCREEN addresses grand societal challenges, builds upon/integrates Europe's preexisting assets in chemical biology, improves the competitiveness of the European Research Area (ERA), and provides scientists with high-quality services.</p> <p>Participation in the EU-OPENSSCREEN saves time/cost and allows member countries to showcase national research/achievements on an international stage.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External stakeholder meetings / one-on-one discussions
General public	Chemical biology and early drug discovery research is highly relevant to society, as it helps us identify valuable new substances like potential medicines.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media • Mass media • Website • Local events for citizens

Alignment with IMPULSE workplan

WP1 Long-term sustainability & access procedures

Part of IMPULSE WP1 will be to engage with international scientific communities to expand the reach of EU-OPENSSCREEN. Planned activities include holding workshops in both European and non-European countries to inform the local scientific communities about ERIC activities, with the goal of attracting new member countries and/or users to the network. Educational workshops in particular will aim to provide local researchers with the skills and knowledge needed to work with EU-OPENSSCREEN as a user.

WP2 Creating a repository of community compounds

IMPULSE WP2 aims to expand the EU-OPENSSCREEN compound-sharing initiative, in which chemists submit compounds to our European Academic Compound Library (EACL). WP2 plans several communication actions for this task:

- Coordinated outreach through a network of national ambassadors in each country represented in IMPULSE to liaise with potential compound submitters and communicate the benefits, requirements and legal aspects of compound submission
- Maintain a website about the initiative to increase transparency and provide easy access to key information about the EACL
- Approach charities, companies and open-source drug discovery initiatives to discuss the submission of compound sets to the EACL

The goal of these targeted outreach efforts is to foster a community of chemists and encourage more chemists to engage with our network.

WP3–6 New scientific services and data management protocols

IMPULSE WP3–6 develop and validate new scientific services for the EU-OPENSSCREEN portfolio and refine data management practices/operational standards across all partner sites. All communication and dissemination assets within the Consortia will be used to distribute information about these developments and secure their uptake by the partner sites offering the services and the scientific community utilising them. These actions will begin later in the project timeline once significant progress has been made in these WPs.

WP7 Training and capacity building

IMPULSE WP7 offers curated training programmes for members of both the Consortia and the external scientific community. Training for external scientists represents a critical form of outreach, as this group represents a pool of future users of EU-OPENSSCREEN services.

Training events will be developed to maximise the visibility of the Consortia within the framework of the activity. IMPULSE WP7 will also tailor training opportunities to early-career scientists, a stakeholder group not currently targeted with other EU-OPENSSCREEN training and outreach efforts.

All communication and dissemination assets within the Consortia will be used to promote IMPULSE training opportunities.

WP8 Engagement with public–private initiatives

In the past, EU-OPENSSCREEN has engaged with private institutions through an Industry Liaison Office (ILO). Under IMPULSE WP8, the ILO will convene regularly to define strategies to engage new private institutions and industry stakeholders. The ILO represents the primary contact point between EU-OPENSSCREEN and private institutions and will communicate the messages outlined above ('Audiences').

WP9 Outreach & Dissemination

IMPULSE WP9 is responsible for overseeing the communication of the IMPULSE project and aligning with EU-OPENSSCREEN outreach activities. WP9 utilises the present Communication Plan to raise awareness of the developments occurring across all IMPULSE work packages.

Working group

The IMPULSE communication and dissemination plan will be executed by the WP9 lead (EU-OS) with support from the WP9 Working Group, consisting of communication officers and other members of the consortium interested in promoting the visibility of the Consortia. This working group meets bimonthly to discuss communication/dissemination strategies and their implementation according to this Communication Plan.

2.4 Key performance indicators

Raising awareness among the broader scientific community of the opportunities for external scientists to advance their own research is key to attract scientific users. The following key performance indicators (KPIs) are collected manually by the EU-OPENSSCREEN central office to monitor the outreach activities:

- Number of newsletters
- Number of newsletter recipients
- Number of website views
- Number of posts on LinkedIn
- Number of posts on X/Twitter
- Number of followers on LinkedIn and Twitter
- Views of posts/tweets
- Number of policy-related activities and related publications

3 Conclusions/Next steps

In this Communication Plan, we provide partners in both the EU-OPENSSCREEN and IMPULSE consortia with the tools needed to effectively communicate about and dissemination their missions, news and actions to the scientific community. By implementing this plan across all partner sites, the Consortia will be able to project a unified message to external audiences about our activities and attract new users and funders to secure the sustainability of our services.

This Communication Plan will be updated as needed throughout the IMPULSE project lifetime to ensure that communication and dissemination actions align with the needs and resources of the scientific community and the Consortia.

Table 3 History of changes

Date	Change(s) applied
30.08.2024	Version 1 established

